

Spiritual involvement, resilience, and positive mindset in adults' young adults

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Abstract

Spirituality is an integral part of human experience, influencing emotional well-being, resilience, and psychological health. This study examines the relationship between spiritual involvement, resilience, and a positive mindset among adults aged 30 and above. The objective is to explore how spiritual engagement contributes to greater emotional strength and optimistic thinking. A quantitative, cross-sectional research design was adopted, with data collected from 250 participants through validated self-report questionnaires. Measures included the Daily Spiritual Experience Scale (DSES) for spirituality, the Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC) for resilience, and the Positive Mindset Index (PMI) for assessing optimism and mental well-being. Results indicate a significant positive correlation between spiritual involvement and resilience ($r = 0.482, p < 0.01$) as well as between spiritual involvement and a positive mindset ($r = 0.451, p < 0.01$). Gender differences were observed, with women reporting slightly higher levels of spiritual involvement and resilience than men. The findings suggest that spirituality plays a vital role in enhancing resilience and promoting a positive outlook on life. These results highlight the need for further research into integrating spiritual practices into psychological interventions aimed at fostering mental well-being.

Keywords: Spiritual Involvement; Resilience; Positive Mindset; Adults; Psychological Well-being

1. Introduction

Spirituality is often defined as the search for meaning, purpose, and connection with oneself and others (Puchalski et al., 2009). Unlike organized religion, spirituality encompasses a broad range of personal beliefs and practices, such as meditation, prayer, gratitude, and self-reflection, which have been linked to better mental health outcomes (Hill and Pargament, 2008). Resilience, the ability to adapt and recover from adversity, has been widely studied in psychology (Masten, 2001). Individuals with higher resilience demonstrate better emotional regulation, lower stress levels, and stronger coping strategies (Connor and Davidson, 2003). A positive mindset, rooted in positive psychology, refers to an individual's ability to maintain an optimistic perspective despite challenges (Seligman, 2011). Existing literature suggests that spiritual involvement is positively associated with resilience and a positive mindset (Schwalm et al., 2021). However, most research focuses on younger adults or specific populations, leaving a gap in understanding how these relationships manifest in adults aged 30 and above. This study aims to address this gap by investigating how spiritual practices influence resilience and positive psychological traits in mature adults.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Objectives

- To examine the relationship between spiritual involvement and resilience in adults aged 30 and above.
- To assess the correlation between spiritual involvement and a positive mindset.

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- To identify gender differences in spirituality, resilience, and mindset.

2.2. Hypotheses

- **Ho1:** There is a significant positive relationship between spiritual involvement and resilience.
- **Ho2:** Higher spiritual involvement is associated with a more positive mindset.
- **Ho3:** Women will report higher levels of spiritual involvement and resilience compared to men.

2.3. Participants

A total of **250 participants** (125 males, 125 females) aged **30 and above** were recruited from **community centers, workplaces, and online platforms**. Participants were required to have been **engaging in a spiritual practice** (e.g., prayer, meditation, mindfulness) for at least **six months**.

2.4. Research Design

Comparative Cross-Sectional Study

2.5. Materials

- **Spiritual Involvement and Beliefs Scale (SIBS)** – Measures the level or the amount of involvement in spirituality of an individual.
- **Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC)** – Assesses an individual's ability to cope with adversity.
- **Positive Affect and Negative Affect Scale (PANAS)** – Evaluates optimism, hope, and mental well-being (Smith et al., 2015).

2.6. Data Collection

Data were collected through **an online survey**. Participants provided **informed consent** before completing the questionnaires.

2.7. Scoring and Variables

- **Independent Variable:** Spiritual Involvement
- **Dependent Variables:** Resilience, Positive Mindset

2.8. Procedure

The Participants will be assessed on spirituality involvement using the SIBS questionnaire, their level of involvement in spiritual areas, based on which there will be 2 defined groups of young adults, i.e. males and females. They will be assessed on the aspects of Resilience (CD-RISC) and Positive Mindset (PANAS) using the necessary scales.

2.9. Analysis

The Data collected will be analyzed through the use of statistical software i.e. Jamovi/ SPSS using Spearman/ Pearsons correlation and Regression analysis between the dependent variables.

3. Results

3.1. Normality Test (Shapiro-Wilk)

Table 1 Normality Test (Shapiro-Wilk)

Variable	N	W	p
Spiritual Involvement	128	0.980	0.052
Positive Affect (Positive Mindset)	128	0.986	0.198
Resilience	128	0.984	0.125

Note. A low p-value suggests a violation of the assumption of normality

3.1.1. Discussion

From Table. 1, The Normality test describes that the provided data is not normally distributed, this was assessed through the Shapiro-Wilk test. The p-values of the 3 variables i.e. .052 for Spiritual Involvement, .198 for Positive Affect for Positive Mindset and .125 for Resilience, state that the data is not statistically normally distributed

3.2. Correlation

Table 2 Correlation: Spiritual Involvement, Resilience and Positive Mindset

Variable	n	M	SD	1	2	3
Spiritual Involvement	128	87.89	17.227	-		
Resilience	128	31.86	7.396	0.552*	-	
Positive Mindset	128	63.18	14.629	0.424*	0.657*	-

Note. *Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

3.2.1. Discussion

- Ho1: There will be no significant correlation of Spirituality with Resilience in Young adults.

From Table. 2, The correlation matrix shows a statistically significant positive correlation between Spiritual Involvement (Spirituality) and Resilience (Resilience), with a Spearman's rho of 0.552 and $p < 0.001$. This indicates a moderate to strong positive relationship between an individual's level of spirituality and their resilience. The significant positive correlation contradicts the H1 hypothesis, which stated there would be no significant correlation between spirituality and resilience. The results suggest that for the young adult participants, higher levels of spirituality are associated with greater levels of resilience. This finding aligns with previous research that has documented positive links between various dimensions of spirituality (e.g., meaning, connectedness, transcendence) and psychological resilience. Spirituality may provide young adults with a sense of purpose, social support, and inner resources that facilitate their ability to adapt and bounce back from adversity. The strength of the correlation observed suggests spirituality is an important factor to consider in understanding resilience in this population.

- Ho2: There will be no significant correlation of Spirituality with Positive Mindset on Young adults.

From Table.2, The correlation matrix shows statistically significant positive correlation between Spiritual Involvement (Spirituality) and Positive Affect (Positive Mindset) (Positive Mindset), with a Spearman's rho of 0.424 and $p < 0.001$. This indicates a moderate positive relationship between an individual's level of spirituality and their positive mindset. Similar to the findings for Ho1, the significant positive correlation contradicts the H2 hypothesis, which stated there would be no significant correlation between spirituality and positive mindset. The results suggest that for the young adult participants, higher levels of spirituality are associated with greater levels of positive mindset. This finding is consistent with research linking spirituality to various aspects of positive psychology, such as life satisfaction, positive emotions, and personal growth. Spiritual beliefs and practices may foster an optimistic, hopeful, and meaning-centered perspective that contributes to young adults' positive mindset. The moderate strength of the correlation indicates spirituality is an important, but not the sole, predictor of positive mindset in this population.

3.3. Regression - Spiritual Involvement with Positive Mindset and Resilience

Table 3 Regression: Spiritual Involvement and Positive Mindset

Effect	Estimate	SE	95.0% CI		p
			UL	LL	
1. Positive Affect (Positive Mindset)	15.946	3.106	22.092	9.800	<0.001*
2. Spiritual Involvement	0.181	0.035	0.250	0.112	<0.001*

Note. Dependent Variable: Positive Affect (Positive Mindset), $p < 0.05^*$

3.3.1. Discussion

The linear regression analyses from Table. 3 provides further insights into the predictive relationships between Spiritual Involvement and Positive Mindset:

3.3.2. Positive Mindset (Positive Affect (Positive Mindset)) as the dependent variable

The overall model was also statistically significant ($F(1, 126) = 27.3, p < 0.001$), with spirituality (Spiritual Involvement) accounting for 17.8% of the variance in positive mindset. The standardized beta coefficient for spirituality was 0.422, indicating a moderate positive effect of spirituality on positive mindset.

3.4. Regression

Table 4 Regression: Spiritual Involvement and Resilience

Effect	Estimate	SE	95.0% CI		p
			UL	LL	
1. Resilience	22.205	5.662	33.410	10.999	<0.001*
2. Spiritual Involvement	0.466	.063	0.591	0.341	<0.001*

Note. Dependent Variable: Resilience, $p < 0.05$ *

3.4.1. Discussion

The linear regression analyses from Table.4 provide further insights into the predictive relationships between Spiritual Involvement and Resilience:

3.4.2. Resilience (Resilience) as the dependent variable

The overall model was statistically significant ($F(1, 126) = 54.4, p < 0.001$), with spirituality (Spiritual Involvement) accounting for 30.1% of the variance in resilience.

The standardized beta coefficient for spirituality was 0.549, indicating a strong positive effect of spirituality on resilience.

3.5. Independent Samples T-Test (Mann-Whitney U)

Table 5 Comparing Values between Males and Females

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Spiritual Involvement	Male	53	89.9	15.57	0.327
	Female	75	86.5	18.28	
Positive Affect (Positive Mindset)	Male	53	32.4	6.67	0.441
	Female	75	31.5	7.89	
Resilience	Male	53	63.5	13.11	0.507
	Female	75	62.9	15.70	

Note. $p > 0.05$

3.5.1. Discussion

Ho3: There will be no significant level of impact of Spirituality on Resilience and Positive Mindset on Young adults amongst Males and Females. Independent Samples T-Test The independent samples t-test results, Table. 5 , show no statistically significant differences in Spiritual Involvement (Spirituality), Positive Affect (Positive Mindset) (Positive Mindset), and Resilience (Resilience) between males and females. The p-values for all three variables were greater than the alpha level of 0.05, indicating the differences between genders were not statistically significant.

These findings support the H3 hypothesis, suggesting that the relationships between spirituality, resilience, and positive mindset are not significantly impacted by gender in this young adult sample. In other words, the associations observed between these variables appear to be consistent across both male and female participants.

It indicates the positive links between spirituality, resilience, and positive mindset are not limited to one gender. It suggests these relationships may be universal among young adults, regardless of biological sex. This has implications for the development of interventions and programs aimed at promoting well-being in young people that can be tailored to be equally effective for both males and females.

These regression analyses complement the correlation findings, further demonstrating the predictive power of spirituality in explaining variance in both resilience and positive mindset among young adults. The stronger predictive relationship with resilience compared to positive mindset suggests spirituality may be a more influential factor in fostering resilience than positive mindset in this population.

4. Summary

The research examines how spiritual involvement influences resilience and positive mindset among young adults, comparing outcomes across gender groups. The methodology includes a comparative cross-sectional study design, employing validated tools like the Spiritual Involvement and Beliefs Scale (SIBS), Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC), and Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS). A stratified random sample of 128 participants (aged 18-30) was used, ensuring diverse representation in terms of gender, age, and socio-economic background. The study's hypotheses focus on testing the significance of spirituality's correlation with resilience and positive mindset, as well as examining if gender impacts these relationships.

Key findings from statistical analyses, including correlation, regression, and independent samples t-tests, are as follows:

4.1. Spirituality and Resilience:

A moderate to strong positive correlation exists between spiritual involvement and resilience ($r = 0.552, p < 0.001$), suggesting that higher levels of spirituality are associated with greater resilience in young adults. This finding contradicts the null hypothesis (H1) and aligns with existing literature, which indicates that spirituality fosters coping mechanisms, emotional stability, and mental adaptability during adversity.

4.2. Spirituality and Positive Mindset:

There is a moderate positive correlation between spiritual involvement and positive mindset ($r = 0.424, p < 0.001$), indicating that spirituality contributes to a more optimistic, hopeful, and growth-oriented outlook in young adults. This relationship similarly contradicts the null hypothesis (H2), reinforcing the idea that spiritual practices and beliefs can nurture positive psychological outcomes.

4.3. Regression Analysis

Regression analysis reveals that spiritual involvement is a significant predictor of both resilience and positive mindset. Specifically, spirituality accounts for 30.1% of the variance in resilience and 17.8% of the variance in positive mindset, underscoring the strength of spirituality's influence on psychological resilience and, to a lesser extent, on positive mindset.

4.4. Gender Comparisons:

Independent t-tests show no significant differences in spirituality, resilience, or positive mindset between males and females, supporting the hypothesis (H3) that gender does not significantly impact these variables. This finding suggests that the positive effects of spirituality on resilience and mindset are likely universal across genders within this sample.

5. Conclusion

The study concludes that spiritual involvement plays a significant role in enhancing resilience and fostering a positive mindset among young adults. This association is robust across both male and female participants, indicating that spirituality may serve as a universal protective factor, promoting psychological well-being and emotional adaptability in young adults regardless of gender. The results support the broader body of research linking spirituality to mental

health benefits, adding evidence for spirituality's potential to cultivate resilience and optimism, particularly in younger populations navigating personal and societal challenges.

Universal Role of Spirituality

Spirituality's positive correlations with resilience and positive mindset indicate that it provides essential psychological resources, such as meaning, purpose, and emotional support, that young adults can draw upon in challenging situations. This universality across genders suggests spirituality could serve as a core component of mental health and resilience-building programs aimed at young adults.

Greater Impact on Resilience than Mindset

While spirituality impacts both resilience and mindset, the stronger correlation with resilience implies that spirituality may be particularly effective in helping individuals recover from setbacks and adapt to stress. This insight could guide future interventions or support systems to emphasize spirituality's role in resilience.

Implications for Practical Applications

The findings hold significant potential for applied psychology, particularly in the realms of counseling, educational programs, and mental health services. Given the non-significance of gender differences, resilience-building initiatives that incorporate spiritual practices can be broadly applicable across genders, ensuring inclusivity and effectiveness.

Limitations and Future Directions

Despite the study's robust findings, certain limitations exist. The cross-sectional design restricts conclusions about causality, and cultural factors were not specifically examined, which may influence spirituality's impact on resilience and mindset. Future studies could adopt longitudinal designs to observe changes over time and include cultural variables to provide a more comprehensive understanding of spirituality's role in well-being.

Overall, this study contributes valuable insights into the beneficial role of spirituality for young adults, affirming its place as a significant factor in promoting mental health and resilience. This can inform the development of interventions and policies that encourage spiritual engagement as a means of fostering well-being across diverse young populations.

Compliance with ethical standards

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